

Open Retail Centre Boundaries for the UK and Their Utility for Functional Analysis and Policy

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Summary

This paper presents an updated methodology for delineating retail centre boundaries across the United Kingdom, building upon Macdonald et al. (2022). The approach integrates open source Foursquare Places point-of-interest (POI) data with OpenStreetMap land use polygons, employing hexagonal spatial aggregation (H3) and network-based connected component identification. Key improvements include Leiden community detection to partition large connected city or town centres into distinct subcentres and automated detection of car-oriented retail parks based on the presence of characteristic big-box chain brands. The centre boundary utility is demonstrated by a case study focused on night-time economy. This shows how consistent spatial definitions enable meaningful integration of heterogeneous data sources, including event listings and opening hours data, supporting nuanced assessment of urban evening economies across multiple dimensions of activity.

KEYWORDS: retail centres, point-of-interest data, hexagonal tessellation, community detection, open data

1. Introduction

The spatial delineation of retail centres is essential for understanding urban economic geography and informing planning decisions. Town centres and high streets form the social and commercial cores of UK cities, characterised by clusters of retail alongside supporting businesses and leisure offerings (Macdonald et al., 2022). Yet there is no uniform definition of what constitutes a town centre, and beyond traditional central locations, retail agglomerations also occur along arterial roads, in neighbourhood centres, and in out-of-town retail parks (Teller & Reutterer, 2008). Retail agglomerations form part of a complex system that constantly evolves, with spatial extents expanding or contracting in response to changing consumer behaviour (Wrigley & Dolega, 2011). Depicting their spatial extent at national scale is pivotal for understanding relationships between retail space and consumer behaviour, and for monitoring economic performance (Pavlis et al., 2018; Newing et al., 2015).

The computation of such definitions presents longstanding methodological challenges. Early UK town centre boundaries used kernel density estimation with socio-economic variables (Thurstain-Goodwin & Unwin, 2000). Pavlis et al. (2018) employed modified DBSCAN clustering using proprietary Local Data Company data. In 2022, we published an open dataset using Valuation Office Agency (VOA) and OpenStreetMap data with H3 hexagonal tessellation, identifying 6,423 retail agglomerations (Macdonald et al., 2022). This paper adopts Foursquare Places as the POI data source. Several limitations motivated this revision. First, VOA data presented geocoding challenges. Second, VOA data covers only England and Wales, requiring supplementary OSM data for Scotland and Northern Ireland. Third, advancements in global POI data, particularly Foursquare Places with pre-geocoded coordinates and temporal metadata, enable more robust boundary delineation.

This paper presents an updated methodology with four key innovations: (1) a POI quality filtering pipeline leveraging closure dates and brand matching; (2) integration of OpenStreetMap land use polygons to reduce false positives; (3) application of the Leiden community detection algorithm to partition large city and town centres into distinct subcentres and (4) a parallel pathway for explicit detection of retail parks based on big-box brand matching, replacing the post-hoc identification used in the original methodology.

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2. Data Sources

Point-of-Interest Data: Foursquare Places POI data covering the UK provides hierarchical category classifications, pre-geocoded coordinates, business names, and temporal metadata including closure dates. Unlike VOA data, Foursquare coordinates require no external geocoding. This work uses data from the Foursquare Places dataset, licensed under the Apache License 2.0.

Land Use Data: OpenStreetMap land use polygons for retail, commercial, and industrial categories. Following Macdonald et al. (2022), retail polygons extend centre boundaries beyond individual POI locations, addressing cases where retail parks have large physical extents (e.g. car parks) but limited address points. Commercial and industrial polygons enable filtering of false positives.

Other Reference Data: The ONS Postcode Directory provides coordinate validation. Local Authority District boundaries enable administrative attribution. A curated list of approximately 180 defunct UK retailer brands supported quality filtering.

3. Methodology

The methodology comprises 13 stages. Stages 1–2 filter the POI data, which then feeds two separate boundary delineation processes: Stages 3–9 identify traditional centres while Stages 10–11 identify retail parks. Stages 12–13 integrate the outputs of each pathway into a single set of non-overlapping boundaries.

3.1 POI Quality Filtering (Stages 1–2)

Stage 1 applies seven sequential filters to remove low quality or outdated POI from the Foursquare data: (i) removal of POIs with closure dates; (ii) pattern matching against defunct retailer brands (e.g., Woolworths, BHS, Blockbuster); (iii) spatial filtering to UK boundary; (iv) detection of non-UK addresses via postal pattern matching; (v) coordinate validation against ONSPD with 1000m tolerance, extending the approach of Macdonald et al. (2022); (vi) duplicate detection using spatial proximity (<15m), category matching, and fuzzy name similarity; and (vii) business succession handling retaining only the most recent establishment at each location.

Stage 2 applies retail category filtering using Foursquare's taxonomy. Inclusion criteria capture Retail, Dining and Drinking, and Arts and Entertainment categories, plus selected services (banks, post offices). This aligns with VOA and OSM categories identified by Macdonald et al. (2022). Exclusions remove non-retail destinations and automated service points.

3.2 Traditional Centre Detection (Stages 3–9)

This pathway detects traditional retail centres characterised by dense, typically walkable, clusters of retail units. Stage 3 aggregates POIs to H3 hexagonal cells at resolution 11. Following Macdonald et al. (2022), H3 provides consistent cell geometry reducing biases from irregular administrative boundaries, and efficient adjacency identification without complex spatial operations.

Stage 4 constructs networks from adjacent cells meeting a minimum POI threshold (≥ 2). This threshold follows Macdonald et al. (2022), who noted single-unit cells indicate low-density areas such as freestanding stores. Connected components are identified using graph algorithms (Csardi & Nepusz, 2006).

Stage 5 removes networks below a minimum POI count (10), derived from UK retail planning policy identifying 10 units as minimum viable clusters (Wrigley & Lambiri, 2015; Pavlis et al., 2018).

Stage 6 applies gap filling to recover interior single-unit cells pruned in Stage 4.

Stage 7 employs Leiden community detection (Traag et al., 2019) to identify subcentres within large networks (≥ 1500 POIs), addressing cases where connected components join distinct functional centres. The algorithm partitions the H3 adjacency network using edge weights based on pairwise retail density similarity. This identifies boundaries where centres are connected by only a narrow corridor of cells or where retail concentration changes.

Stage 8 filters false positives by computing overlap with OSM commercial and industrial polygons; small centres (≤ 20 POIs) with significant ($>75\%$) overlap are removed.

Stage 9 merges fragmented centres separated by single empty cells, analogous to the 36 mergers from stakeholder consultation in the original methodology.

3.3 Retail Park Detection (Stages 10–11)

A parallel pathway detects car-oriented retail parks, which exhibit distinct spatial morphologies with lower POI densities across larger areas (Thomas et al., 2006). The original methodology identified retail parks post-hoc; this revision implements explicit detection.

Stage 10 identifies retail parks by spatial joining POIs to OSM retail polygons, computing the proportion matching big-box retailer brands (e.g., B&Q, Currys, IKEA). Polygons exceeding 5% brand match and 0.07 km² minimum area are classified as retail parks.

Stage 11 merges spatially adjacent parks.

3.4 Integration and Finalisation (Stages 12–13)

Stage 12 integrates traditional centres and retail parks, excising retail park cells from overlapping traditional centres.

Stage 13 dissolves H3 cells to polygon boundaries and computes attributes including POI counts by category, area, density, and Local Authority assignment.

4. Validation and Results

Validation combined automated checks with expert consultation. Following Macdonald et al. (2022), an interactive web map was developed for ground-truthing. Workshops with academic researchers, local authority planners, and commercial sector representatives reviewed centres in their areas of expertise, identifying boundaries requiring adjustment. The method was iteratively refined based on stakeholder feedback, with thresholds initially informed by prior work and subsequently adjusted through consultation.

Of venues marked as open in the Foursquare dataset, approximately 7% fail the custom quality filters and are removed. Retail category filtering then retains approximately 34% of quality-filtered POIs. The commercial and industrial land use filter removes 604 incorrectly identified centres in areas associated with non-retail industries such as offices and logistics facilities.

The pipeline produces boundaries broadly consistent with the previous version while addressing key limitations. The updated methodology identifies more centres with typically larger extents. This reflects both the incorporation of the new POI source and the explicit retail park pathway, which captures car-oriented centres previously identified only through post-hoc adjustment.

5. Case Study: Mapping the Retail Centre Function at Night

The utility of the retail centre boundary framework is demonstrated through a case study of night-time economy activity in Liverpool. This study draws on Smart Data sources obtained from the Geographic Data Services (GeoDS), using the boundaries as a consistent spatial denominator to integrate and compare diverse datasets. The analysis focuses on opportunities for activity that occur after 17:00 to isolate the specific pulse of the evening economy. Two datasets are utilised; the first is from Data Thistle and relates to events listings and venue data (<https://data.geods.ac.uk/dataset/event-listings-and-venue-data>); and the second is Local Data

Company retail type and location data (<https://data.geods.ac.uk/dataset/local-data-company-retail-type-vacancy-and-address-data>).

Figure 1 Spatial distribution of night-time economic indicators across retail centres in Liverpool

Figure 1 illustrates how these retail centre boundaries function as a practical container for data describing two sets of activities: the realised cultural programming captured via Data Thistle event listings (Figure 1a) and the evening opportunities for retail activity derived from Local Data Company (LDC) opening hours (Figure 1b). In Figure 1a, events scheduled for 2025 between 17:00 and 05:00 are aggregated to the centre boundaries, revealing the intensity of cultural activity. This perspective demonstrates how the boundaries effectively capture "realised" entertainment activity by providing a clear extent for point-based event data.

In contrast, Figure 1b maps the concentration of late-opening retail units, where "evening-active" status is defined by units remaining operational after 17:00. This distribution reflects the underlying commercial infrastructure, with high counts typically indicating established clusters of hospitality and leisure venues. Viewed together, these maps emphasise the practical application of the boundary framework; despite coming from entirely different providers and representing different types of urban phenomena, the retail centre boundaries allow these datasets to be integrated and interpreted from a more holistic perspective. This case study provides additional confirmation that the proposed boundaries are not merely theoretical but serve as a robust tool for multi-source triangulation and policy application. By anchoring heterogeneous datasets to a standardised definition of "centre," the framework provides a reliable foundation for researchers to analyse the multi-dimensional nature of the urban night-time economy.

6. Conclusion

This study presents an updated methodology for delineating retail centre boundaries across the United Kingdom, addressing key limitations in Macdonald et al. (2022) with the implementation of a new POI data source, land use-informed boundary refinement, community detection for partitioning large centres, and explicit detection of car-oriented retail parks. The approach integrates Foursquare Places data with OpenStreetMap polygons, maintaining open data principles while improving robustness and reproducibility. Validation through stakeholder consultation confirms boundaries align with planning practice and local knowledge. The night-time economy case study demonstrates practical utility, showing how consistent spatial definitions enable meaningful integration of heterogeneous data sources including event listings and opening hours data, that capture different dimensions of urban evening activity. This supports policy applications requiring integrated assessment of retail centre performance. The framework's reliance on openly available data ensures reproducibility and supports ongoing monitoring of UK retail landscapes, contributing to evidence-based planning and economic geography research.

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Biographies

Dr Zihan Yin is a Senior Data Scientist at the Geographic Data Service, University of Liverpool. Her research lies at the intersection of applied microeconomics and spatial data science. She specialises in spatial data analysis, visualisation of economic patterns, and integrating large-scale geographic datasets into empirical economic research.

Dr Owen Goodwin is a Senior Data Scientist at the Geographic Data Service and University of Liverpool. He holds a PhD in experimental particle physics from the University of Manchester. His research develops data science and machine learning methods for large-scale geographic datasets, with current projects on geodemographic classification and retail centre delineation.

Dr Les Dolega is a Senior Lecturer at the Department of Geography at the University of Liverpool. Les is an expert in retail geography, consumer behaviour and area classifications. He has led a number of research projects related to retail including ‘e-Resilience’/vulnerability of British retail centres to the impacts of internet sales, delineation of retail centre boundaries and developing a national typology of retail centres in the UK. Most recently he has led a project creating an Ageing in Place Classification and its real-world applications to estimating housing satisfaction, loneliness and service provision for older people in England. He was also a Co-I on a Consumer Data Research Centre grants where he was leading a key research pathway related to retail and consumer data.

Alex Singleton is Professor of Geographic Information Science at the University of Liverpool and Director of the Geographic Data Service. His research sits at the boundary between the social and computational sciences; and has extended a tradition of area classification within Urban Analytics where he has developed an empirically informed critique of the ways in which geodemographic methods (unsupervised machine learning) can be refined for effective yet ethical use; and how systems comprising artificial intelligence can assist in public resource allocation applications. This research has developed from substantive interests

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